

The Most Important Number in the Whole Multiverse - 8T

O Manor

June 11, 2021

Abstract:

In this paper, analysis of the vibrational Lorenz manifold (M, g_E) with signature $(3,1)$, which is the connected manifold, $M = M_0 \times R$, invoked stationary, by the Euler Lagrange operator will be made regarding two symmetry breaking processes, the coupling constant series, correlated to a symmetry breaking due to the majestic (3) , or $8 + (1)$ variations, alongside the other symmetry breaking, mass attaining associated with the $8 - (1)$ variations and endless families forming below first generation quarks.

Introduction

The coupling constant primordial equation:

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.11)$$

The masses series equation:

$$M_{N+1} = \frac{M_N + (7)}{7 * \prod_{i=1}^r N_E} * \frac{1}{9} \quad (1.12)$$

$$M_{N+1} = \frac{M_N + (7)}{7 * \prod_{i=1}^r N_E} * \frac{1}{9} \quad (1.121)$$

$$N_E = 2E; E \geq 1$$

The symmetry break associated with $8 + (1)$ variations, is creating the coupling constant series and the bosonic propagation outward. The symmetry breaking due to the opposite transformation $8 - (1)$ is associated with generation of masses, or arbitrary variation propagating inward, giving us the masses series and the infinite families forming below first generation. Eight is indeed the most important number in the entire universe, and all the universes wrapping our own.

$$8 + (1) \rightleftharpoons 8 + 0 \quad (2.1)$$

$$8 - (1) \rightleftharpoons 8 + 0 \quad (2.11)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)